

BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES

POTENTIAL PATHOGENIC CHARACTERISTICS OF MICROMYCETES INHABITING DENTAL CLINICS

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Abstract

The presented work is dedicated to the study of the structural composition and pathogenicity characteristics of the nosocomial mycobiota formed in dental clinics. It was found that the mycobiota formed in dental clinics consisted of 30 species of fungi belonging to 12 genera. It was determined that representatives of 3 genera, including *Penicillium*, *Aspergillus* and *Candidum*, are widespread in dental offices and make up 63.3% of the total mycobiota. As well as, unstable environmental factors in dental offices have been shown as the main reason for the high pathogenicity of nosocomial mycobiota.

Keywords: dental clinic, micromycetes, species diversity, density of fungi, pathogenic activity, environmental factors.

It is as a result of this that the transformation of saprotrophic species of microscopic fungi living in various anthropogenic environments, including health facilities, into clinical biological organisms is being observed with increasing dynamics. Therefore, pathogenic microscopic fungi gaining a superior position in anthropogenic environments, at the same time negatively affecting people's health, causing the emergence of various pathologies [1;3;4;9].

It is known that the difference in the general level of patients applying to healthcare facilities, including dental clinics, is taken into account in regulating the temperature of the room. Even in the warm seasons of the year, air conditioners are used more often in the ventilation system of rooms. This affects the balance of environmental factors in dental offices and the increase of humidity indicators. As a result, the reproductive energy of microscopic fungi, especially potential pathogens, increases, which gives a strong impetus to their massive sporulation process. Thus, the concentration of microscopic fungi in the atmospheric air of dental offices increases significantly, and their contamination with patients leads to various mycotic pathologies, including dermatomycosis, allergic infections, aspergillosis, candidiasis, etc. is observed by its manifestation [2;8;10;11].

The aim of the presented work was to study the structural organization of nosocomial mycobiota formed in dental clinics and the eco-biological characteristics of their pathogenic species.

Material and methods

The Republican Stomatology Center, the dental clinic of AMU and 5 dental offices operating in Baku were selected as research objects and studied from the mycological aspect. The sedimentation method was used to take samples from the air environment of dental rooms. At this time, Petri dishes filled with Çapek-Doks or Saburo nutrient media were kept open for 30 minutes at a height of 1-1.5 m from the ground. At the

same time, samples were taken from the surface of the floor, ceiling, walls, medical instruments of the room, as well as from the oral cavity of the patients by the application method and inoculated in the indicated food environments. Colonies were counted on the 7th day of cultivation. The obtained results were expressed by calculating CFU either in Im^3 air or in 1 g of applied material. In order to obtain a pure culture, it was considered appropriate to conduct the experiments in 4-6 repetitions. Known determinants were used to identify and determine species affiliation of the studied mushroom species.

The frequency of occurrence of fungi is expressed by increasing the ratio of the studied species to the total number of mycobiota by 100 times. Those with more than 40% are considered dominant, those between 20-40% are common, and those below 20% are considered rare [5;6; 7].

Results and discussion

In the course of the research, it became clear that a unique mycobiota is formed in each healthcare facility, including dental facilities, depending on its purpose. It should be noted that during the treatment works carried out in the stomatological cabinets, including the grinding of teeth, the processing for the purpose of adjusting the prostheses in the oral cavity causes the formation of enough dust particles. It creates conditions for bioaerosolization of microscopic fungi that spread in the atmospheric air of these rooms. during the treatment of patients, certain microdamages of the mucous membrane in the oral cavity to a certain extent, the destruction of the enamel layer of the teeth, the same cleanings to a certain extent, maceration of the epithelial tissue of the skin material, etc. cases like this happen. As a result, bioaerosolized microscopic fungi that spread chaotically in the air environment of dental offices migrate very easily to the oral cavity or respiratory organs when patients speak or breathe. If we also take into account the presence of people with low immune

status among patients, then it is inevitable that dermatomycosis, allergic infections, including aspergillosis and candidosis pathologies will appear quickly. Because the favorable conditions created in the air environment of dental offices lead to significant activation of potential pathogens, which stimulates the process of mycogenic sensitization of patients. This leads to the emergence of systemic secondary pathologies in people

with low immune status. At the same time, the occurrence of mycotic pathologies in dental clinics directly depends on the density and pathogenic activity of microscopic fungi spreading in the air.

In the course of the research, it became clear that mycobiota formed in medical institutions, including dental clinics, and called nosocomial, exhibit specific characteristics both in terms of gender composition, species diversity, and pathogenic activity (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Characterization of nosocomial mycobiota in dental clinics by gender

Thus, the conducted comparative studies show that the species belonging to the genera *Humicola*, *Rhizomucor* and *Sporotrichum* are permanent members of the nosocomial mycobiota formed in various healthcare facilities. Since the frequency of the mentioned fungi in dental institutions is less than 20%, they are considered rare fungi. Nevertheless, rare fungi are directly involved in the formation of the dominant core of nosocomial mycobiota. Thus, the dominant core of nosocomial mycobiota in dental clinics has 9 members and is characterized by the following composition: *Aspergillus clavatus*, *A. fumigatus*, *Penicillium capsulatum*, *P. decumbens*, *Candida albicans*, *C. krusei*, *Humicola grisea*, *Rhizomucor pusillus*, *Sporotrichum pruinosum*. At the same time, these fungi have opportunistic properties and show sufficient pathogenic activity.

Despite the high level of sanitary-hygienic work, fungi characteristic of dental clinics and offices, including *Aspergillus clavatus*, *A. fumigatus*, *Alternaria alternata*, *Candida albicans*, *C. krusei*, *Cladosporium cladosporioides*, *Eurotium amstelodami*, *Geotrichum candidum*, *Humicola grisea*, *Penicillium desumbens*, *P. chrysogenum*, *Scopulariopsis brevicaulis*, *Sporotrichum pruinosum*, *Rhizomucor pusillus* always maintain their presence. It seems that this situation has a lot to do with the substrate specificity of the characteristic fungi. Also, since the mentioned characteristic fungi have opportunistic properties, they are directly involved in the emergence of exogenous or endogenous mycotic pathologies in the body.

The instability of environmental factors in dental offices leads to an increase in the pathogenic activity of the constituent elements of nosocomial mycobiota, which creates a real basis for the infection of these and other mycotic pathologies in patients who come for treatment. Therefore, it is very necessary to regularly conduct mycological monitoring in dental clinics and offices.

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